

Original Article

A Cointegration Time Series Analysis of Long Run Relationship between Petroleum Product Prices and Inflation

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Abstract

This study focuses on finding the long run relationship between different income group-based index numbers, i.e., lower, higher, and combined/average income groups with that of petroleum products prices, namely petrol and high-speed diesel (HSD). Another focus of the study is estimation of an equation to investigate the effect of petrol and HSD prices on different income groups, and to assess which income group is affected more by increase in prices of petroleum products for the period 1991-2021. Necessary tests are used to assess the nature of stationarity after which Johansen's cointegration test is used to assess the long run equilibrium relation. The long run cointegration equation helps in assessing the strength of petrol and HSD on increasing the consumer price index for different income groups. From the study, it is found that for lower income group HSD causes more change in the index number than that of petrol prices while for higher income group families the case is reverse. Whereas for combined income group high speed diesel revealed more changes than that of petrol.

Keywords: Petroleum, Inflation, High Speed Diesel, Time Series Analysis, Consumer Price Index

Introduction

Oil prices play vital role in the economic activity of every country specifically for oil importing countries. The two mostly dependable areas on oil are industries and transportation. In country like Pakistan, approximately 60% of energy is produced by Petroleum Products. Thus, it is of major interest for everybody to know the impact of oil prices on different important indicators of economy. One of the most important economic indicators which plays vital role in national policy matters is inflation, which is defined as the increase in the prices of different commodities for a specific time. The tool used to assess the inflation figure is Consumer Price Index (CPI). The percentage change in the CPI for one fiscal period over the other fiscal period is defined as inflation, e.g., if CPI for the period 2011-12, 2010-11 was 162.57 and 146.45, respectively then the percentage change, 11.01 is defined as inflation for the period 2011-12 (PBS, 2012). It is of interest to know that oil prices have a valuable weight in the compilation of CPI. Thus, it is significant to find out the impact of petroleum products on inflation figure.

The Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (PBS), also known as Federal Bureau of Statistics in the past, is responsible for compilation and publication of Price Indices and different important statistics.

Consumer Price Index (CPI) is a significant measure of inflation used worldwide to reflect any change in the prices of basket of specified representative items, reflecting general patterns of common people's daily consumption. The first ever CPI published by PBS was compiled with base period as 1948-49 for industrial workers (PBS website), for which the data was collected from the cities of Sialkot, Lahore, and Karachi. To have better coverage of the items and cities, the number of cities and items have been added and changed at each family budget survey for CPI. Up till now CPI is compiled based on following base years; 1959-60, 1969-70, 1975-76, 1980-81, 2000-01 and 2007-08.

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According to the publication of Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, CPI based on base period 2007-08 covers 40 urban centers of Pakistan comprising 76 markets and 5 income groups. The detail of income group is as under:

- Q1:** Up to eight thousand rupees.
- Q2:** From eight thousand and one to twelve thousand rupees.
- Q3:** From twelve thousand and one to eighteen thousand rupees.
- Q4:** From eighteen thousand and one to thirty-five thousand rupees.
- Q5:** Above thirty-five thousand rupees.

Whereas the combined income group measures the average of all income groups-based index number. As per the publication of PBS, CPI for the current base period, i.e., 2007-08, covers 487 items. The items are selected based on family budget survey conducted in 2007-08. Current CPI may be divided into 12 groups. The weights of commodity groups reveal that after food group the most highly weighted groups are housing, water, electricity, gas and other fuels and transportation with weights 34.84, 29.41 and 7.20 respectively. This is why the study of petroleum products is of major importance for many researchers and policy makers.

The methodology used for the computation of CPI uses the formula of Laspeyre's as given below:

$$I_n = \frac{\sum (P_n/P_o) \times W_i}{\sum W_i} \times 100$$

Where,

- I_n = Consumer Price Index for the nth period
- P_n = Price of an item in the nth period.
- P_o = Price of an item in the base period.
- Q_o = Quantity of an item used in the based period.
- W_i = Weight of the ith item in the base period = $\sum P_o \times Q_o$
- $\sum W_i$ = Total weight of all items.

Besides CPI, Pakistan Bureau of Statistics also compiles Wholesale Price Index and Sensitive Price Indicator. WPI is computed on monthly basis while SPI is computed and published each week. These important indicators are used by different government departments for policy purposes.

WPI and SPI also use the same formula of Laspeyers. WPI covers 463 items while SPI covers most essential 53 kitchen items (PBS, 2012). The world in aggregate is in the grip of rising inflation. Pakistan is not an exception. The general CPI for the month of March 2013 reached to 175.82 (with base period 2007-08=100), whereas the Transport Index approached to 189.11 for the same period (PBS, 2013). It is said that inflation, if it goes beyond the double digit, is an indication of a weak economy.

According to Aurangzeb and Haq (2012), inflation is said to exist if the demand of daily use commodities is more than their production. They further state that deflation and increased supply of currency notes, deprived performance of agriculture sector, worldwide high oil prices, maximum use of ethanol fuel, hoarding and smuggling are also the main cause of high inflation. The study also revealed that as much the loan of the country increases, it increases the inflation rate.

The rising prices of commodities, specifically of petroleum products, are causing economic hurdles for families with low income. In addition, the devaluation of currency is exaggerating the level of poverty in the country. Electricity shortages have badly affected many economic hubs and industries. Thus, potentially effective economic policies can help to deal with the intensifying inflationary movement and improve the exaggerated divisions of the economy, specially manufacturing and agriculture.

Motivation

Petroleum products play a vital role in the economic activity of every country specifically for oil importing countries. Many of the researchers have studied the impact of oil prices on the economy in combination with other variables like interest rate, household expenditure, crops etc. in different countries including Pakistan. But an individual study on measuring the effect of petroleum products on the Consumer Price Index (CPI) is not carried

out in Pakistan. Thus, there is a dire need to investigate the nature of the relationship between petroleum products and inflation in the context of Pakistan.

Objectives

The main objectives of this study are:

- To investigate the trend in prices of petroleum products and inflation time series data
- To determine the equilibrium relationship between petroleum product prices and inflation.
- To assess the long-run relationship b/w Petroleum products prices and inflation

Literature Review

Several researchers from all parts of the world worked on different aspects of economy and tried to find out the impact of different factors that contribute to the economic growth.

Jones and Khilji (1988) used the Granger direct test to examine if there exist any relationship between inflation and growth in money supply in the context of Pakistan for the period starting from 1973 to 1985. The results of the study revealed that money growth had a significant influence on inflation during the period considered and vice versa.

Abbas and Mitchell (2002) studied the effect of petroleum prices on the economy and the distributional price rise impact of petroleum products. They used modified input output approach to see the impact of petroleum prices on the economy in Australia. Their results indicated that hypothetical price increase would raise the CPI by 1.8%. Cunado and Gracia (2005) examined the effect of oil price changes on economic activity and CPI for six Asian countries (Singapore, South Korea, Japan Malaysia, Philippines and Thailand) for the period 1975 – 2002. The results suggested significant impact of oil prices on economic activity and price indices.

Perera (2005) tried to investigate different factors in Sri Lanka. It was shown that diesel prices have direct impact on price indices. He used autoregressive distributed lag model and revealed that the indirect impact of changes in diesel prices on Colombo Consumers Price Index (CCPI) and Sri Lanka Consumers Price Index (SLCPI) was bigger than the direct impact. An increase of 10% in diesel prices would yield an increase of 1.21% in CCPI during the first month. Whereas for SLCPI the indirect impact of the similar change in diesel price was 1.01 % with a lag of two to three months. The author applied cointegration tests and found that variables were not significantly cointegrated.

Schimmelpfennig (2006) determined the forecast inflation in Pakistan based on money supply, the interest, and the exchange rates; credit to the private sector, also the wheat support price was taken as a supply-side factor. Their results revealed significant impact of money supply with a lag of one year. According to technical report of State Bank of Pakistan (2008), for oil importing country like Pakistan, oil prices scramble quickly entered into the domestic economy and inflated the energy shortage in Pakistan which caused increase in the general price level.

Malik (2008) investigated the challenges of high oil prices on the economy of Pakistan. As Pakistan is heavily dependant on imported fuels which is expected to increase causing inflationary pressure on the economy. Cologni and Manera (2008) estimated a vector autoregressive model for G7 countries to see if changing oil prices for the last 20 years have been reflected in policy matters. They introduced long & short run relationships between oil prices, interest rate and inflation. Their Results suggested that, for most of the G7 countries considered, an unexpected oil price change was followed by a rise in inflation rate and by a decrease in output growth.

Syed (2010) measured the impact of oil prices and other macro-economic variables like consumption, inflation and foreign direct investment, etc. on Gross Domestic Product (GDP) for Pakistan's economy.

Baker (2011) examined the effect of oil prices on inflation and observed that oil prices were affecting more to the lower income group families as compare to higher income group. Study also revealed that fuel expenditure cause twice the total budgets of low income consumers than that of economically stable consumers. Alvarez et. al. (2011) assessed the impact of oil price changes on Euro and Spanish area consumer price index and revealed that the effect of oil price changes in both economies was partial, even though crude oil price oscillations were main casue of inflation inconsistency. The effect on Spanish inflation was found to be somewhat bigger than in the Euro area. The direct effects have increased in both economies, in the last decade, showing that the consumers pay more on refined oil products than that of other kitchen items.

Celik and Akgul (2011) studied the changes in fuel oil prices and their relationship with Consumer Price Index (CPI) in Turkey from 2005-2010 using Vector Error Correction model. Their results revealed that 1% rise in fuel oil prices increased CPI by 1.26% with an approximate one year lag.

Le and Chang, (2011) examined the reaction of stock markets to oil price volatilities in Singapore, Korea, Japan and Malaysia and used the generalized impulse response and variance decomposition analyses approach to the monthly data from 1986 – 2011. Their results revealed that the response of stock markets to oil price shocks changes significantly through markets. Abdullah and Kalim (2012) tried to investigate the main factors contributing to food inflation based on Johansen's cointegration approach for the period 1972-2008, and revealed a long term relationship between inflation and factors like inflation expectations, support prices, etc.

Ali et. al. (2012) found a significant relationship between factors. According to Economic Survey of Pakistan (2012), worldwide rise in commodities and fuel prices activated significant rise in domestic inflation. The report suggested that main factor responsible for the rise of non-food inflation was the increase in the prices of oil, gas and energy items. The ramble in the prices of petroleum products, such as, petrol, kerosene oil, HSD, gas, CNG and electricity tariff rates, etc., caused increase in cost of general daily use items, which as a result caused increase in the general level of inflation.

Methodology

This section will discuss various topics of econometric used for analysis of time series data, together with description about the source of data to be used for the purpose of study.

Data Source

Data to be used for the study purpose will be obtained from the Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (PBS) fiscal year monthly basis, starting from July 1991 to June 2021. Data will be collected for consumer price index (CPI) for lower, higher, and combined income groups, and petroleum products which include petrol and high-speed diesel (HSD) prices.

Statistical Analysis

In this study, first the trend and nature of trend of data would be assessed with the help of correlogram. To see the effect of stationarity of the data several unit root tests are available. Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and Phillips-Perron (PP) test would be used in this study to decide about the presence or absence of stationarity in the data. If the data is found to be non-stationary, then first difference of the given time series will be checked for stationarity. After the presence of non-stationarity, co-integration would be studied to assess if there exist any long run relationship between index number and petroleum products. After that cointegration regression equation will be used to see the significance of the coefficients in the long run and to see the significance of those coefficients in the regression model. To achieve the mentioned objectives of the research, Eviews version 8 (2013) is used as statistical software for time series data analysis.

Time Series Data

Time series data plays vital role in the theory of econometrics and is used to reflect significant and important underlying patterns in the given data set. Whenever data is arranged in the form of a series in a chronological order or with respect to time is referred to as time series data. The data may be collected for some characteristic of interest and observed over different time points. Time series data can also be collected at any point of time depending on the underlying study needs and objectives. For example, the hourly electricity consumption data collected by American electricity distribution to know the electricity load at peak hours. Data may also be collected on daily, weekly, monthly annual basis, for instance data collected on daily basis by price monitoring wings of government of different commodities in order to keep check and balance in the market or the weight of new born children recorded on monthly basis by the health physician to keep a track of growth or the monthly prices of commodities collected by PBS for the compilation of CPI, or the annual GDP figures published by PBS. The census data of Australian Bureau of Statistics available for every five years or the census of manufacturing data of Pakistan, etc.

Modeling of Time Series data

The duty of a statistician regarding time series data is to develop a statistical model for the time series data in such a way that it incorporates major characteristics of a particular time-based data set, logical mathematical form, easy

in terms of interpretation, potentially capable of predicting the unknown future phenomena of a particular response and have the ability of drawing inference about the significance of parameters involved in the model. Earlier knowledge about the pattern of time series data was examined by decomposing it in secular trend, seasonal trend, cyclical variation and irregular or random variation despite the fact that how well the model forecast the time series data. But with the passage of time things got changed and now much of it is studied through advanced time series approaches. Mathematically the basic form is given as

$$Y_{t+1} = Y_t + U_{t+1}$$

Where Y_t may be assumed as the price of a particular commodity at a particular time point t and U_{t+1} is the random error at time point $t+1$. This model is also referred to as autoregressive model. One of the basic assumptions considered for making prediction of a given time series is that the series has zero mean and a constant variance. A series having this property is known as stationary time series. If the given series is not stationary then it is converted to stationarity by means of differencing (Enders, 2004). Now a detailed discussion is made about stationary and non-stationary time series.

Stationary Time Series

One of the major objectives before initiating any time series analysis is to investigate if the given series is stationary or not. That is, if the series has a constant variance and mean and the covariance is associated among the jumps of two consecutive points only, then it is said that the given time series data is stationary. In other words, a time series is said to be covariance stationary at two different time points say t and $t-k$, if the following conditions hold:

$$E(X_t) = E(X_{t-k}) = \mu$$

$$Var(X_t) = Var(X_{t-k}) = \sigma^2 > 0$$

$$Cov(X_t - X_{t-k}) = \gamma_k$$

The equations reflect that the mean is constant, variance is homoscedastic, and both are independent of time factor, while covariance is linked to the jump points only and is k difference apart. If any data set does not obey these conditions, then it is said that the time series is non-stationary (Gujrai, 2004).

Non-Stationary Time Series

A time series is said to be non-stationary if one or more of these characteristics are fulfilled, that is, its mean, variance and covariance are time dependent. If such a time series is displayed graphically, will reflect some trend. Most of the time series data available are non-stationary by nature. The disadvantage of having such a time series is that projection cannot be made. As one of the major interests of a statistician is to do projection of unknown future phenomenon based on available information. Therefore, it is essential to convert the existing non-stationary time series to stationary time series by taking its difference (Gujrati, 2004).

Procedure to Test Stationarity

Several procedures are available to test if the given data set is stationary or not. For this study following procedures will be used.

Correlogram Test

One of the simplest procedures to check the presence of stationarity in the given time series is to graphically display the data set through correlogram approach. The core idea is to draw autocorrelation functions of the given time series against the time lag. If the image display of correlogram reveals trend of autocorrelation function values of a given time series data around zero at different lags, then this is an indication of stationarity, while if the autocorrelation function values are high in the beginning and decline linearly or show tendency to zero but very slowly even after many lags is an indication of non-stationarity. Autocorrelation function at lag k is represented by ρ_k and defined as under

$$\rho_k = \text{Covariance at lag } k / \text{Variance}$$

$$\rho_k = \gamma_k / \gamma_0$$

The autocorrelation function is unit less measure and ranges from -1 to 1.

Autocorrelation Function (ACF)

When interest lies in finding the linear relationship between observations of the same variable at different time lags, the term ACF is used, which is given as:

$$\rho_k = \frac{Cov(X_t, X_{t-k})}{Var(X_t)}$$

$$\rho_k = \gamma_k / \gamma_0, \quad -1 < \rho_k < 1$$

Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF)

Partial autocorrelation function is obtained when the effect of intervening variables, $X_{t-1}, X_{t-2}, \dots, X_{t-k+1}$ has been removed while calculating the correlation between X_t , and X_{t-k} . it may also be said that PACF investigates the strength of relationship between any observation at a particular current time point with that of any other observation at lag k , after controlling the effect of observations that are in between the lags (i.e. lags $< k$).

Q Statistics

The autocorrelation of all the observations up to a certain lag can be tested simultaneously with the help of Q-Stat and its probability, which is given by

$$Q = n \sum_{i=0}^k \hat{\rho}_k^2$$

The test checks if the given series has some white noise or not.

Unit Root Test

Unit root is nothing but a tool a check if the given time series is stationary or non-stationary. The name is because in the model given below if $\rho = 1$, it causes the presence of non-stationarity. The tool is very productive and is widely used for many years due to its simplicity and easy interpretation. The model to check the presence or absence of stationarity is given as

$$Y_t = \rho Y_{t-1} + e_t \quad -1 \leq \rho \leq 1$$

Where Y_t reflects a time series process, e_t is random error and also popularly known as white noise. It is of interest to know that a number of procedures exist to check the problem of unit root. The most common of these are Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and Phillips-Perron (PP) test.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller test (ADF)

One of the most used approach to investigate the presence or absence of stationarity in a given time series is modified and augmented form of Dicky and Fuller test, known as Augmented Dicky Fuller test. The main objective of the test is to check if given time series has the problem of unit root or not. If the value of the coefficient of lagged variable in a time series econometric model is found to be equal to one, then it is an indication of unit root problem in the given time series.

In order to proceed with the analysis, the criteria is to estimate the coefficient values of the underlying model, that is to estimate γ .

$$\Delta X_t = \gamma X_{t-1} + \alpha_2 \Delta X_{t-1} + \alpha_3 \Delta X_{t-2} + \dots + \epsilon_t \quad \text{Random Walk.}$$

Random Walk with Drift.

Random Walk with Drift and trend

One of the assumptions while testing the problem of unit root in the above model is to consider that $X_0 = 0$ and $\epsilon_t \sim \text{iid } N(0, 1)$. The hypothesis considered by ADF test is that the coefficient value is equal to zero against the alternative that it is not equal to zero. The decision criteria is that

1. If the computed value of the ADF test statistic exceeds critical value, it leads to the conclusion that the given series has the problem of unit root.
2. If the calculated value of the test statistic is less than the tabulated or critical value, then it leads to conclusion that there does not exist the problem of unit root in the given time series.

If the conclusion leads to the fact that there is the problem of unit root in the given time series, take the difference of the time series and then check again the same procedure. It is of interest to know that most of the time series show stationary pattern after the difference has been taken.

Phillips-Perron (PP) Test

One of the important considerations of Dicky Filler test while testing the problem of unit root is that the white noise terms are identical and independent, but it is not the case. So, to overcome this problem lagged observations are included in the model to tackle the serial correlation. This is a parametric approach. The same problem of serial correlation is tackled by a different approach by Phillips-Perron. Phillips Perron introduced a test to check the presence of unit root in the time series model by assuming a non-parametric criterion to tackle the problem of serial correlation. By doing so they overcome the addition of lagged difference terms to the model. It is of importance to know that the asymptotic distribution of PP test is the same as that of ADF test.

Cointegration

Two or more time series might be non-stationary but stationary at first difference. Interest may be to check if the linear combination of these non-stationary time series is stationary at no difference or zero difference. If such characteristic exists then such series/variables are said to be cointegrated, or in other words there may exist a long run equilibrium relationship between them. Let us consider X_t and Y_t as stationary time series at first difference, then

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_t + e_t$$

Where $e_t \sim I(0)$

Then X_t and Y_t are cointegrated and their regression is called cointegration regression. One of the most used methodologies to test the presence of cointegration is Johansen's approach. The model of vector autoregression (VAR) is specified as below

$$y_t = \mu + A_1 y_{t-1} + \dots + A_p y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t$$

Where μ is the vector of intercepts having order $n \times 1$, while y_t represents integrated variables of order one, i.e, $I(1)$ and is represented by a vector of order $n \times 1$, ε_t is the error term represented by an $n \times 1$ vector. The model can also be written as

$$\Delta y_t = \mu + \Pi y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \Gamma_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t$$

Where

$$\Pi = \sum_{j=1}^p A_j - I \text{ and } \Gamma_i = - \sum_{j=i+1}^p A_j$$

Where Π is the coefficient matrix. Now if it has reduced rank i.e., $r < n$, it is said that there exist $n \times r$ matrices α and β . The rank of both matrices is r in such a way that $\Pi = \alpha\beta'$ and β' , then Y_t becomes stationary. Here r represents the number of cointegrating relationships, α is known as the adjustment parameter in the vector error correction model, while columns of β represents cointegrating vector. To test the significance of cointegrating relationship, Johansen introduced two approaches namely trace statistic and maximum eigen value test.

Trace Statistic

The main idea of trace statistic is to test if there exist no more than r cointegrating relationships against the alternative that there exist more than r cointegrating relations. To test this the test statistic used is given by

$$\lambda \text{ trace } (r) = -T \sum \ln(1 - \lambda)$$

Where T represents the number of observations while λ represents the estimated eigen values.

Maximum Eigen Value Statistic

Instead of stating more than r cointegrating relations in alternative hypothesis as supposed in the case of trace statistic is to consider only $r + 1$ relations. The approach used to test this kind of relation is given by maximum Eigen value and is defined as

$$\lambda \text{ max } (r, r+1) = -T \ln(1 - \lambda_{r+1})$$

Results and Discussion

Graphical Presentation of Data

This section describes the graphical presentation of the data for the three indices series and two petroleum products for the period from July-1992 to June 2012. Correlogram approach is adopted to represent if there is any stationarity in the data. One of the problems in correlogram is to select appropriate lag length, but Eviews-8 statistical software, automatically selects lag length. The lag length in the given graphical analysis is 36. However, a general approach is to calculate autocorrelation function up to one third the length of the understudy time series (Gujrati, 2004)..

Figure 1
Correlogram for Combined Index Number

The autocorrelation coefficients (ACF) for combined index number in figure 4.1 start from a very high value of (0.982) and then shows a linear decline which indicates non stationarity in the index number based on combined income group for the period starting from July,1991 to June 2012. From most of the lines in the ACF column are to the right of solid vertical line, which indicates positive relationship between the observations. On the other hand, PACF of combined index number has only one significant spike at lag 1. This also gives a rough idea that mean, and variance of the time series is time variant.

Figure 2
Correlogram for Q1 (lower income group) Index Number

The autocorrelation coefficients (ACF) for Quintile1, i.e. lower income group based index number in figure 4.2 shows that the values of ACF starts from (0.983) and then drops down very slowly towards zero, which reveals non stationarity in the lower income group based index number for the period starting from July,1991 to June, 2012. The PACF for lower income group-based index number has only one significant spike at lag 1. It can also be observed that most of the lines in ACF column are to the right of solid vertical line, giving an idea about the invariant property of time series.

Figure 3
Correlogram for Q5 (higher income group) Index Number

The autocorrelation function (ACFs) for Quintile 5, i.e., higher income group-based index number in figure 4.3 reflects same pattern of ACF coefficient values as observed in the lower income group based index number. Same conclusion may be drawn, that is non in the higher income group-based index number for the period starting from July 1991 to June, 2012 the data reveals non stationary pattern.

Figure 4
Correlogram for Petrol Prices

The autocorrelation functions (ACFs) for petrol prices in figure 4.4 displays that the coefficients of ACF starts from a very high value of (0.982) and then decreases very slowly towards zero. Whereas PACF for petrol prices has two significant spikes at lag one and two respectively. On the basis of the above discussion, it may be concluded that, the time series of petrol prices depicts non stationarity for the period starting from July, 1991 to June, 2012.

Figure 5
Correlogram for HSD Prices

Figure 5

The autocorrelation coefficients (ACFs) for High-Speed Diesel prices in figure 4.5 starts from a very high value of (0.982) and then decreases very slowly, indicating non-stationarity in the HSD prices for the period starting from July,1991 to June 2021.

Similar trends are observed in almost all five-time series. The PACF reveals two significant spikes for high-speed diesel prices. Thus, it can be concluded that all the above series exhibit the pattern of non-stationarity.

To overcome the problem of non-stationarity, first difference of the given series is taken, and it is observed that all series converges to stationary time series.

Figure 6
Correlogram after 1st difference of Combined Index Number

The spikes in the autocorrelation function after taking first difference of combined income group-based index number in figure 4.6 shows tendency of the spikes towards center, which indicates stationarity in the data set for combined income group based index number for the period starting from July, 1991 to June, 2021.

Figure 7
Correlogram after 1st difference of QI Index Number

The barbs in the autocorrelation function after taking first difference of Q1, i.e lower income group-based index number in figure 4.7 indicates tendency of the spikes towards solid vertical line, which indicates stationarity in the data set for quintile 1 or lower income group based index number for the period starting from July, 1991 to June, 2021.

Figure 8
Correlogram after 1st difference of Q5 Index Number

The first difference of the given series helped in converting the non-stationary time series to stationary pattern. It can be observed that autocorrelation function after taking first difference of Q5, i.e., higher income group-based index number in figure 4.8 shows tendency of the spikes towards center, which indicates stationarity in the data set for quintile 5 or higher income group-based index number for the period starting from July, 1991 to June, 2021.

Figure 9
Correlogram after 1st difference of Petrol Prices

The correlogram of petrol prices after taking first difference reveals tendency of autocorrelation coefficients towards vertical line, which indicates that the given time series is stationary. i.e., the data set for petrol prices for the period starting from July 1991 to June, 2021 is stationary at first difference.

Figure 10
Correlogram after 1st difference of HSD Prices

The correlogram of high-speed diesel prices after taking first difference reveals tendency of autocorrelation coefficients towards vertical line, which indicates that the given time series is stationary. i.e., the data set for high-speed diesel prices for the period starting from July 1991 to June 2021 is stationary at first difference.

Time Series Analysis

The time series analysis consists of

- i) Unit root test for stationarity
- ii) Cointegration test to assess the presence or absence of cointegration between different indices and petroleum products.
- iii) Estimation of cointegration regression equation.

Unit Root Test

Based on EViews statistical software, Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests are used to check unit root in the given series of indices and petroleum products, which by default selected the the lag length of 15 for ADF test. Both intercept and trend are used in the analysis for detecting the presence of unit root problem.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) Tests

Table 1

Unit Root Test for Stationarity in Combined Index Number

Test	Test Statistic value	C.V at 1%	C.V at 5%	C.V at 10 %	Result
ADF	2.536228	-3.99504	-3.42783	-3.137268	Non-Stationary
PP	3.007294	-3.99504	-3.42783	-3.137268	Non-Stationary

Table 1 shows that calculated values of test statistic (2.536228), based on ADF test is less than the critical values at one, five and ten percent respectively. Thus, the given hypothesis cannot be rejected, and it may be concluded that the combined index number has a unit root. It means that there exists a unit root which implies that the combined index number series is non-stationary. Similarly, the test statistic value of (3.007294) calculated based on PP test is also less than the critical values at one, five and ten percent respectively. This also leads to the acceptance of null hypothesis about the presence of unit root problem or non-stationarity in the time series for combined index number.

Table 2

Unit Root Test for Stationarity in Q1 (lower income group) Index Number

Test	Test Statistic value	C.V at 1%	C.V at 5%	C.V at 10 %	Result
ADF	1.627932	-3.99504	-3.42783	-3.137268	Non-Stationary
PP	2.003275	-3.99504	-3.42783	-3.137268	Non-Stationary

Table 2 shows that the calculated value of test statistic is (1.627932) calculated on the basis of ADF test is less than the critical values at one, five and ten percent respectively. Thus, the given hypothesis cannot be reject and it may be concluded that the lower income group based index number has a unit root, OR It may be concluded that there exist a unit root problem, which implies that the lower income group based index number series is non-stationary at 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance, respectively.

Similarly, the test statistic value of (2.003275) computed on the basis of PP test also leads to the acceptance of null hypothesis at one, five and ten percent level of significance respectively. It may be concluded that the given time series is non-stationary.

Table 3

Unit Root Test for Stationarity in higher income group Index Number

Test	Test Statistic value	C.V at 1%	C.V at 5%	C.V at 10 %	Result
ADF	2.705567	-3.99504	-3.42783	-3.137268	Non-Stationary
PP	3.326911	-3.99504	-3.42783	-3.137268	Non-Stationary

Table 3 shows that the computed values of test statistic based on ADF and PP test are less than the critical value at one, five and ten percent respectively, thus the said hypothesis about the non-stationarity of higher income group based index number may be accepted and it may be concluded that there exist a unit root which implies that the higher income group based index number series is non-stationary at 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance, respectively.

Table 4

Unit Root Test for Stationarity in Petrol Prices

Test	Test Statistic value	C.V at 1%	C.V at 5%	C.V at 10 %	Result
ADF	-2.959442	-3.995189	-3.427902	-3.13731	Non-Stationary
PP	-2.430828				Non-Stationary

Table 4 shows that the calculated values test statistics are (-2.959442, -2.430828) respectively based on ADF and PP test. Both values lead to the acceptance of the said hypothesis that the petrol prices have a unit root OR it means that the time series of petrol prices is non-stationary at 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance, respectively.

Table 5

Unit Root Test for Stationarity in HSD Prices

Test	Test Statistic value	C.V at 1%	C.V at 5%	C.V at 10 %	Result
ADF	-0.03446	-3.99504	-3.42783	-3.137268	Non-Stationary
PP	0.254732				Non-Stationary

Table 5 shows that the computed values of test statistics based on ADF, and PP test are less than the critical values at one, five and ten percent respectively. Thus, the given hypothesis about the presence of unit root problem in the high-speed diesel prices cannot be rejected. It means that there exists the problem of unit root which implies that the high-speed diesel prices series is non-stationary.

Table 6

Unit Root Test for Stationarity of Combined Index Number after 1st Difference

Test	Test Statistic value	C.V at 1%	C.V at 5%	C.V at 10 %	Result
ADF	-14.71396	-3.995189	-3.42790	-3.13731	Stationary
PP	-14.73979				Stationary

Table 6 shows that after taking the first difference of combined index number, the value of the test statistic is greater than that of critical region value, at one, five and ten percent respectively. Thus reject the said hypothesis that the combined index number has a unit root based on both test statistics, i.e., ADF and PP test. It means that there does not exist a unit root which implies that the combined index number series is stationary at 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance, respectively.

Table 7

Unit Root Test for Stationarity of lower income group-based Index Number after 1st Difference

Test	Test Statistic value	C.V at 1%	C.V at 5%	C.V at 10 %	Result
ADF	-14.28298	-3.995189	-3.427902	-3.13731	Stationary
PP	-14.21045				Stationary

Table 7 shows that after taking the first difference of lower income group-based index number; reject the said hypothesis that the lower income group-based index number has a unit root based on both test statistics, i.e. ADF and PP test. It means that there does not exist a unit root which implies that the lower income group-based index number series is stationary at 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance, respectively.

Table 8

Unit Root Test for Stationarity of higher income group-based Index Number after 1st Difference

Test	Test Statistic value	C.V at 1%	C.V at 5%	C.V at 10 %	Result
ADF	-15.15503	-3.995189	-3.427902	-3.13731	Stationary
PP	-15.15555				Stationary

Table 8 shows that after taking the first difference of higher income group-based index number, the computed values of test statistics based on ADF and PP test are greater than critical values at one, five and ten percent respectively. Thus, it leads to the rejection of said hypothesis that the higher income group based index number

has a unit root based on both test statistics, i.e. ADF and PP test. It means that there does not exist a unit root which implies that the higher income group based index number series is stationary.

Table 9

Unit Root Test for Stationarity of Petrol Prices after 1st Difference

Test	Test Statistic value	C.V at 1%	C.V at 5%	C.V at 10 %	Result
ADF	-12.09057	-3.995189	-3.427902	-3.13731	Stationary
PP	-11.39025				Stationary

Table 9 shows that after taking the first difference of petrol prices, the computed values of test statistics are greater than C.V. at one, five, and ten percent respectively. Therefore, reject the said hypothesis that the petrol prices have unit root based on both test statistics, i.e., ADF and PP test. It also implies that the petrol prices series is stationary at first difference.

Table 10

Unit Root Test for Stationarity of HSD Prices after 1st Difference

Test	Test Statistic value	C.V at 1%	C.V at 5%	C.V at 10 %	Result
ADF	-13.70992	-3.995189	-3.427902	-3.13731	Stationary
PP	-13.56908				Stationary

Table 10 shows that after taking the first difference of high-speed diesel (HSD) prices, reject the said hypothesis that the high speed diesel prices has unit root based on both test statistics, i.e. ADF and PP test. It means that there does not exist a unit root which implies that the high-speed diesel prices series is stationary at 1,5 and 10% level of significance, respectively.

Johansen Test of Cointegration

It is important to decide in advance about the lag length for Johansen test of cointegration, but since the analysis is done by EViews-8 statistical software, which automatically selects suitable lag length. As the analysis is performed for each index number separately based on income groups, i.e., lower, higher, and combined (average), therefore separate three tests of cointegration are performed. The Johansen test uses two methods, λ trace and λ max statistic to find cointegration between variables. And thus, it is the only criteria used in this analysis to decide about the long run equilibrium relationship.

Table 11

Johanson Cointegration Test for (Combined Index Number, Petrol and HSD)

Trace and Eigen Value Statistics					
Statistics	Null Hypothesis	Alt. Hypothesis	Eigen value	Trace Statistic	C.V at 5%
λ trace Statistic	$r = 0$	$r > 0$	0.163993	64.94187	29.79707
	$r = 1$	$r > 1$	0.060943	20.69977	15.49471
	$r = 2$	$r > 2$	0.020708	5.16865	3.841466
λ max Statistic	$r = 0$	$r > 0$	0.163993	44.24211	21.13162
	$r = 1$	$r > 1$	0.060943	15.53111	14.2646
	$r = 2$	$r > 2$	0.020708	5.16865	3.841466

Table 11 is used to test the presence of equilibrium relationship between variables. For this purpose, λ trace Statistic and λ max Statistic are used. The first null hypothesis test that there is no cointegrating (long run) relationship exists among combined index number, petrol and high-speed diesel prices, i.e. $r = 0$, whereas alternative hypothesis states the opposite. It can be observed that the values obtained on the basis of both test statistics are greater than the critical values at 5% level of significance, thus leading to the conclusion that there exists long run relationship between more than zero variables.

The analysis is preceded until the hypothesis for cointegrating relationship fails. The second hypothesis test that there exists long run relationship between only one variable against the alternative that the long run relationship exists for more than one variable, i.e. $r=1$ against $r > 1$. The computed values of trace statistic and max eigen value statistic leads to the rejection of null hypothesis; thus it may be concluded that there exist cointegrating relationship between more than two variables, i.e there exists long run relationship for more than one variables, namely combined index number, petrol prices and high speed diesel prices.

Similar conclusion may be drawn for testing the null hypothesis about cointegrating relationship between three variables, i.e., $r=2$ against the alternative hyp: $r > 2$. The computed values of test statistic led to the conclusion that there exists long run equilibrium relationship for more than two variables, namely combined index number, petrol prices and high-speed diesel prices. In the nutshell it may be said that combined index number, petrol prices and high-speed diesel prices have long run relationship.

Table 12

Johanson Cointegration test for (Q1 (lower income group) Index Number, Petrol and HSD)

Trace and Eigen Value Statistics					
Statistics	Null Hypothesis	Alt. Hypothesis	Eigen value	Trace Statistic	C.V at 5%
λ trace Statistic	$r = 0$	$r > 0$	0.114412	49.95611	29.79707
	$r = 1$	$r > 1$	0.060392	19.94474	15.49471
	$r = 2$	$r > 2$	0.018286	4.558497	3.841466
λ max Statistic	$r = 0$	$r > 0$	0.114412	30.01137	21.13162
	$r = 1$	$r > 1$	0.060392	15.38624	14.2646
	$r = 2$	$r > 2$	0.018286	4.558497	3.841466

Table 12 is used to test the cointegrating relationship between lower income group-based index number, petrol prices and high speed diesel prices. The first hypothesis test there is no cointegrating relationship between lower income group-based index number, petrol prices and HSD price. The computed values of trace statistic and max eigen values are greater than the critical values at 5% level of significance, thus leading to the rejection of null hypothesis and in favor of alternative. The second hypothesis test that there exists cointegrating relation between only one of the variables against the alternative that the relationship exists for more than 1 variable. The test statistic values computed on the basis of trace statistic and max Eigen value leads to the rejection of null hypothesis, thus it may be concluded that there exist cointegrating relationship for more than one variable, namely lower income group-based index number, petrol prices and HSD prices. Same conclusion is drawn for testing $r=2$ vs $r > 2$, i.e., there exists cointegrating relationship between only two variables against the alternative that it exists for more than two variables. In the nutshell it may be concluded that there exists long run relationship between lower income group-based index number, petrol prices and HSD prices.

Table 13

Johanson Cointegration Test for (Q5 (higher income group) Index Number, Petrol and HSD)

Trace and Eigen Value Statistics					
Statistics	Null Hypothesis	Alt. Hypothesis	Eigen value	Trace Statistic	C.V at 5%
λ trace Statistic	$r = 0$	$r > 0$	0.188307	72.58029	29.79707
	$r = 1$	$r > 1$	0.063302	21.04783	15.49471
	$r = 2$	$r > 2$	0.019625	4.895541	3.841466
λ max Statistic	$r = 0$	$r > 0$	0.188307	51.53246	21.13162
	$r = 1$	$r > 1$	0.063302	16.15229	14.2646
	$r = 2$	$r > 2$	0.019625	4.895541	3.841466

The above table reveals similar conclusion as was done previously. The result reveals rejection of null hypothesis based on both test statistic values at 5% level of significance about no cointegration relationship, one cointegration relationship and two cointegration relationship. Thus, it may be concluded that there exist a long run relationship between higher income group based index number, petrol prices and high speed diesel (HSD) prices.

Cointegrating Equation

Next objective of the study is to see which income group is more vulnerable to the changes in the prices of petroleum products, i.e., petrol and diesel. For this purpose, long run cointegration regression is used, which yielded the following estimated equations. The first Cointegration regression equation represents higher income group-based index number (Q5) regressed on the prices of Petrol and HSD as given below:

$$Q5 = 30.7263 + 0.7716 * PETROL + 0.6435 * HSD$$

It reveals that if petrol price is increased by one-rupee, higher income group based index number (Q5) will increase 0.7716 times, whereas if High Speed Diesel price increases by one rupee, it will cause an increase of 0.6435 times in the index of higher income group. Thus, it can be visualized that petrol causes more change in the index for higher income group than that of HSD. This conclusion may also be because, in general higher income group families rely more on personal/private transportation source, which uses petrol as a source of energy. Thus, higher the prices of petrol, higher would be index number for higher income group-based families. The constant term of 30.7263 reveals the effect of other items/commodities that are not taken into consideration of this study. It should be noticed that there are 463 total items used for the compilation of consumer price index number and this study focuses only on two items.

Contrary to the above estimated equation the results for lower income group are reverse. The index number for Quintile1 that is, the index number based on lower income group, when regressed on petrol prices and high-speed diesel generated the following results:

$$Q1 = 31.9558 + 0.6303 * PETROL + 0.7867 * HSD$$

It can be observed that if petrol price rises by one-rupee, lower income group-based index number (Q1) will grow 0.6303 times, and if High Speed Diesel price rises by one rupee, it will cause an increase of 0.7867 times in the index of lower income group-based families. It is obvious from the result that the index number for lower income group-based families is affected more by high-speed diesel prices as compared to petrol prices. The hidden fact behind this picture is that majority of lower income family's travel in public and local transport, like buses, which uses HSD as a source of energy. Thus, Government should pay more attention on keeping the rates of HSD as low as possible in order to facilitate the lower income group families.

When the combined income group-based index number is regressed on the prices of petrol and HSD, displays the following results:

$$\text{Combined} = 32.2141 + 0.6963 * PETROL + 0.7029 * HSD$$

The equation shows that if petrol price is increased by one rupee, then combined income group index will increase 0.6969 times, whereas if High Speed Diesel price increases by one rupee, then it will cause an increase of 0.7029 times in the index of combined income group. Thus, it can be imagined that HSD causes more change in the index for combined income group than that of petrol.

In the nutshell it may be concluded that for lower income group based families, HSD prices are more significant, and for higher income group based families petrol prices rises play the key role in triggering the inflation figures. But overall HSD prices brings more change than petrol prices for the combined/average index number. This is because majority of people in the country are poor and mostly depend on cheap source of traveling.

Conclusion

The main aim of the study is to find out the long run relationship between consumer price index for lower, higher and combined income group with that of the prices of petrol and high-speed diesel. For the said purpose monthly data was collected from PBS for 20 years. The data was analyzed with the help of correlogram and unit root tests, which suggested presence of unit root, while the first difference of the available series revealed stationarity. ADF and PP tests were used to assess the presence of stationarity. After confirming for non-stationary, Johansen's cointegration test was used to see the long run equilibrium relationship between consumer price index and petroleum products which revealed significant relationship between the variables of interest. After this cointegration regression equation was used to assess the strength of each variable on consumer price index. The results for lower income group suggested higher impact of HSD prices on index number than that of petrol prices, while the case was totally opposite in higher income group, which showed that petrol prices were more affecting increase in consumer price index for higher income group families than that of HSD prices. The case of combined income group showed that overall HSD prices were causing more increase in the combined income group than that of petrol prices.

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